

Donor- π -acceptor based stable porphyrin sensitizers for dye-sensitized solar cells: Effect of π -conjugated spacers

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Abstract

Porphyrins are major sensitizers in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) results in very high power conversion efficiency, however, aggregation tendency and visible range absorption avoids realistic applications. Thus, designing of novel porphyrins based sensitizers are essential to resolve the current existing issues. In this context, seven D- π -A porphyrin dyes (**LG1-LG7**) engineered with 3-ethynyl phenothiazine tethered at the meso-position and π -spacers such as 4-ethynyl phenyl (**LG1**), 5-ethynylthiophene (**LG2**), 5-ethynyl furan (**LG3**), 2,1,3-benzothiadiazole (BTD)-phenyl (**LG6**) and 2,1,3-benzothiadiazole (BTD)-thiophene (**LG7**) were incorporated between porphyrin macrocycle and anchoring carboxylic acid. Similarly, π -spacers 4-ethynyl phenyl (**LG4**) and 4-ethynylthiophene (**LG5**) were functionalized between porphyrin and anchoring cyanoacrylic acid. **LG5** and **LG6** showed significant near infrared absorption resulted highest efficiency of **10.20%** and **9.64%** among other derivatives. UV-vis-NIR absorption, cyclic voltammetry and density functional theory calculations of **LG1-LG7** suggested that **LG5** exhibits strong absorption and optimized lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) aid to inject electrons very effectively from excited state of dye into TiO₂ conduction band. Current density-voltage (J-V) of **LG1-LG7** revealed that **LG5** exhibits highest short-circuit current density of 21.01 mAcm⁻² resulting the power conversion efficiency of **10.20%** in a liquid I⁻/I₃⁻ redox couple electrolyte. Panchromatic IPCE response of **LG5** observed in between 400-900 nm, when compared to other derivatives. Thus, these results suggests that **LG5** attained highest efficiency in liquid electrolyte based DSSC. Subsequently, durability studies of **LG5** performed by continuous light exposure have shown that this sensitizer retained 80% initial efficiency after 1000 h. Therefore, effect of spacer length and anchoring significantly contributed to improve the

efficiency in liquid electrolyte, which is very useful to make the efficient future generated dye sensitized solar cells.

Key Words: Phenothiazine, Porphyrin, Donor- π -Acceptor, Sensitizer, Efficiency, Redox electrolyte.

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1. Introduction

With the potential of becoming a clean and renewable energy source, Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) have drawn much attention because of the relatively high photovoltaic efficiencies, lower production cost and aesthetic features of vivid colour and transparency.¹⁻⁸ Even though DSSC has crossed certified efficiency of >11%, almost all components of the device have to be redesigned to enhance the durability and lead to the effectiveness of the device cost. The sensitizer is one of the indispensable components of the device and extensively used sensitizers are Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes.⁹⁻¹³ Irrespective of their high conversion efficiency, the main drawbacks of Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes are expensive due to the rarity of the metal in the earth's crust, and the lack of absorption in the near-IR region of the visible spectrum, where the solar flux of photons is still significant, thus limiting the realization and usability of highly-efficient devices.⁷ Consequently, dyes with large π -conjugated systems such as porphyrins and phthalocyanines have received considerable attention as sensitizers for DSSC applications.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ Among them Porphyrins and their derivatives have been under intensive investigation not only because of their role in the photosynthetic processes to convert solar energy into free energy, but also due to their strong absorptions in the visible/near-IR region and also ease of structural modification.¹⁸ Additionally, their chemical structures can be steadily modified to understand the effect of structural properties on cell efficiencies.¹⁹⁻²¹

The first porphyrin used for the sensitization of nanocrystalline TiO₂ was the carboxy zinc porphyrin, in which anchoring carboxyl group at *meso* phenyl position was reported with an efficiency of 3.5%.²² Later, the design strategy has been modified in which anchoring carboxyl group is now at its β -pyrrole position since the electron cloud is more concentrated. Based on this concept, Officer and co-workers have reported a variety of β -pyrrole substituted zinc porphyrins and showed light-conversion efficiencies of up to 7.1%.²³

Enormous effort has been put forth in recent years to advance the existing highest power conversion efficiency by various structural modifications at the *meso*-positions of porphyrin macrocycles.²⁴⁻³⁰ Grätzel and several other groups have re-designed the porphyrin sensitizer by adopting donor- π -acceptor (D- π -A) approach, in which an organic molecule having absorption in 450-500 nm region acts as a donor, porphyrin macrocycle as a π -spacer and carboxyl group as an anchoring as well as acceptor group. Porphyrin based sensitizers using this concept have crossed efficiency of 10%. Recently, Grätzel and co-workers have further re-designed D- π -A porphyrin by introducing octyloxy-wrapped structures at *meso* phenyl position, utilizing a benzothiadiazole (BDT) as auxiliary acceptor linked between π spacer and carboxylic acid, reported with a record efficiency of 13%.³¹ The presence of octyloxy-wrapped structure minimizes the recombination of porphyrin macrocycle with electrons in TiO₂ conduction band.

In *meso*-phenyl substituted porphyrins, D- π -A frame work dyes provide a highly flexible platform for the development of single-molecule panchromatic sensitizers.^{32,33} In a typical *meso*-substituted D- π -A dyes, π -spacer and anchoring groups determined not only the light-harvesting characteristics of the chromophores, but also the electron injection rate and the binding energy of the dye on the semiconductor surface.³⁴ However, the research about the combined π -spacer and anchoring group was not fully explored. It was revealed that, in porphyrin dyes, the elongation of π -conjugation or loss of molecular structure symmetry can cause a splitting in π and π^* energy levels and a decrease in the energy gap between HOMO and LUMO, thus resulting in broadening and red shift of the absorption band together with an increasing intensity of the Q band.¹⁵ In addition to that, introduction of auxiliary acceptor between the π -spacer and carboxylic acid, the porphyrin chromophores led to efficiently fill the absorption gap between the Soret band and the Q band in porphyrin dyes, even being capable of avoiding the complementary co-sensitization.³¹

Herein, we focus on a rational approach for systematic improving the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current (J_{sc}), thus pursuing high efficiencies for DSSC applications by changing the π -spacers and anchoring groups. As shown in chart 1, all seven dyes are specifically wrapped with long chain alkyloxy groups and this may retard the unwanted charge recombination process. Phenothiazine is a non-planar butterfly conformation and good electron donor group attached at *meso*-position of porphyrin through ethynyl spacer in **LG1-LG7** sensitizers. Thus, phenothiazine not only acts as donor but also suppressing the

aggregation of porphyrin macrocycle due to its non-planar nature.^{34,35} The implementation of ethynyl bridge between phenothiazine and porphyrin ring will enhance optical properties of sensitizer. Three porphyrin sensitizers **LG1**, **LG2** and **LG3** with phenyl, thiophene and furan as π -spacers and carboxylic acid as anchoring group were tethered in a D- π -A fashion to understand the influence of substitution of π -spacer groups on the light-harvesting ability of the sensitizers. To evaluate the broadened light-harvesting ability of the porphyrin sensitizers **LG4** and **LG5** with phenyl and thiophene as π -spacers and cyanoacrylic acid as an anchoring group were designed and synthesized. Another two sensitizers **LG6** and **LG7** were designed to take an insight into additional auxiliary acceptor as well as the trade-off of long wavelength response by inserting the 2,1,3-benzothiadazole (BDT) group between the π -spacer carboxylic acid (phenyl, thiophene tethered to carboxylic acid) and porphyrin ring.

Chart 1. Molecular structures of the porphyrin sensitizers.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials.

Commercially available reagents and chemicals were procured from Sigma-Aldrich, *Merck*. Analytical reagent (AR) grade solvents were used for the reactions while laboratory reagent (LR) grade solvents were used for purifications and column chromatography. Dichloromethane, chloroform and acetonitrile were dried in presence of calcium hydride under nitrogen atmosphere. Hexane, toluene and tetrahydrofuran were purified by refluxing overnight with Na metal added benzophenone refluxing overnight, then distilled under

vacuum and stored over 4Å molecular sieves. Triethylamine was distilled over NaOH pellets. ACME silica gel (60-120 mesh) was used for column chromatography. Thin-layer chromatography was performed on Merck-pre-coated silica gel 60-F254 plates. Either gravity or flash chromatography was performed for purification of all compounds. All the reactions were carried out under nitrogen or argon atmosphere using dry and degassed solvents.

2.2. Synthesis.

3-bromo-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazene, methyl 4-9-bromobenzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)benzoate were procured commercially. 3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazene (**1**), 4-(7-bromobenzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)benzoic acid (**2**), 5-(7-bromobenzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (**3**) and 5-bromo-15-(Triisopropylsilyl)ethynyl-10,20-bis(2,6-di-octoxy phenyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) (**4**) were synthesized as per literature methods.^{34,36,37}

[3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine-15-(Triisopropylsilyl)ethynyl-10,20-bis(2,6-di-octoxy phenyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) (5). Compound **1** (131.6 mg, 0.393 mmol) and compound **4** (270 mg, 0.196 mmol) was dissolved in 30 ml of THF. To this 5 ml of triethylamine, Pd(PPh₃)₄ (11.3 mg, 0.0098 mmol.) and CuI (1.8 mg, 0.0098 mmol) were added under an inert atmosphere. The reaction mixture was stirred at 40 °C for 24 hours. TLC monitored the completion of the reaction. The solvent was removed by rotary evaporation. The residue was purified by column chromatography (THF/n-hexanes = 1:10, v/v) to give the desired compound **5** (yield = 31%) as a green solid. Anal.Calcd. For C₉₇H₁₂₇N₅O₄SSiZn% (1552.61): C, 75.04; H, 8.24; N, 4.51. Found: C, 74.98; H, 8.20; N, 4.45. MALDI-TOF: m/z [M]⁺calcd. for C₉₇H₁₂₇N₅O₄SSiZn, 1552.61; found,1552.93. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz): δ=9.57 (m, 2 H), 8.76 (t, J=4.7 Hz, 3 H), 7.75 (dd, J=9.0 Hz, 7.1 Hz, 1 H), 7.66 (t, J=8.5 Hz, 2 H), 7.54 (d, J=8.7 Hz, 2 H), 7.36 (t, J=2.1 Hz, 2 H), 7.19 (s, 1 H), 7.13 (dd, J=8.6 Hz, 2.5 Hz, 2 H), 6.99 – 6.97 (m, 4 H), 6.92 (d, J=8.4 Hz,1 H), 6.85 (s, 1 H), 4.12 (t, J=4.6 Hz, 8 H), 3.97 – 3.9 (m, 2 H), 3.81 (s, 3 H), 1.43 (s, 13 H), 1.33 (m, 18 H), 1.29 (s, 16 H), 1.25 (m, 6 H), 0.90 (m, 30 H), 0.60 ppm (s, 10 H). FT-IR (neat, cm⁻¹): 3447, 2922, 2852, 2134, 1633, 1588, 1495, 1461, 1378, 1247, 1208, 1098, 996, 756, 713.

2.2.1. General Procedure for Synthesis of Sensitizers. To a solution of compound **5** (200 mg, 0.122 mmol) in anhydrous THF (20 mL) was added TBAF (0.6 mL, 1 M in THF) and the

reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 30 min under inert atmosphere. The mixture was quenched with H₂O and then extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure.

[5,15-bis(2,6-dioctoxyphenyl)-10-(3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine)-20-(4-carboxyphenylethynyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) LG1. The residue (180 mg, 0.122 mmol) and 4-iodobenzoic acid (145.3 mg, 0.58 mmol) were dissolved in a mixture of anhydrous THF (20 mL) and triethylamine (8 mL) under inert atmosphere. To this Pd₂(dba)₃ (31.3 mg, 0.03 mmol) and AsPh₃ (76.3 mg, 0.2 mmol) were added. The solution was refluxed for 17 h and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by silica gel column chromatography (CH₂Cl₂/MeOH = 20:1, v/v), recrystallized from MeOH/Ether to give the desired sensitizer **LG1** (yield 55%) as a green solid. Anal.Calcd. For C₉₅H₁₁₁N₅O₆SZn% (1516.37): C, 75.25; H, 7.38; N, 4.62. Found: C, 74.52; H, 7.40; N, 4.65. MALDI-TOF: m/z [M]⁺calcd. For C₉₅H₁₁₁N₅O₆SZn, 1516.37; found, 1516.69. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz): δ=9.62 (dd, *J*=4.4 Hz, 2.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.88 (d, *J*=2.3 Hz, 2 H), 8.85 (d, *J*=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.15 – 8.11 (m, 2 H), 7.96 (m, 4 H), 7.71 (d, *J*=5.3, 2 H), 7.56 (d, *J*=8.4 Hz, 4 H), 7.19 (d, *J*=7.4 Hz, 2 H), 7.03 – 7.00 (m, 3 H), 6.93 (d, *J*=24.1 Hz, 2 H), 3.90 (s, 2 H), 3.86 (t, *J*=6.5 Hz, 8 H), 1.28 (t, *J*=13.6 Hz, 6 H), 0.99 (dd, *J*=14.3 Hz, 7.1 Hz, 8 H), 0.89 (t, *J*=6.8 Hz, 3 H), 0.80 (dd, *J*=14.7 Hz, 7.3 Hz, 8 H), 0.65 – 0.58 (m, 10 H), 0.52 (m, 30 H), 0.45 – 0.35 ppm (m, 10 H). FT-IR (neat, cm⁻¹): 3421, 2922, 2852, 2188, 1697, 1629, 1598, 1500, 1459, 1407, 1208, 1095, 760, 553, 458.

[5,15-bis(2,6-dioctoxyphenyl)-10-(3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine)-20-(2-carboxythiophene-5-ethynyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) LG2. We have adopted similar procedure as **LG1**, but only the difference is instead of 4-iodobenzoic acid, 5-Bromo-2-thiophenecarboxylic acid (131.5 mg, 0.63 mmol) was taken. The crude compound was purified by silica gel column chromatography (CH₂Cl₂/MeOH = 18:1, v/v), recrystallized from MeOH/Ether to give dye **LG2** (yield 66%) as a green solid. Anal.Calcd. For C₉₃H₁₀₉N₅O₆S₂Zn% (1522.40): C, 73.37; H, 7.22; N, 4.60. Found: C, 73.32; H, 7.20; N, 4.65. MALDI-TOF: m/z [M]⁺calcd. for C₉₃H₁₀₉N₅O₆S₂Zn, 1522.40; found, 1522.77. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz): δ=9.61 (d, *J*=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 9.55 (d, *J*=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.92 – 8.87 (m, 4 H), 7.89 (d, *J*=3.6 Hz, 1 H), 7.71 (s, 2 H), 7.40 (d, *J*=8.4 Hz, 2 H), 7.32 (s, 4 H), 7.28 – 7.27 (m, 2 H), 7.18 – 7.16 (d, *J*=7.6 Hz, 2 H), 7.05 (d, *J*=7.4 Hz, 2 H), 3.88 (m, 10 H), 1.37 (m, 8 H), 0.94 (m, 12 H), 0.88 (m, 8 H), 0.71 (d, *J*=6.4 Hz, 10 H), 0.59 (m, 29 H), 0.45 ppm (d,

$J=1.5\text{Hz}$, 10 H). FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}): 3445, 2923, 2853, 1620, 1544, 1493, 1459, 1383, 1242, 1206, 1140, 1094, 971, 933, 892, 855, 815, 764, 701, 666, 629, 584, 548, 508, 471, 432.

[5,15-bis(2,6-dioctoxyphenyl)-10-(3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine)-20-(2-carboxyfuran-5-ethynyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) LG3. We have adopted similar procedure as **LG1**, but only the difference is instead of 4-iodobenzoic acid, 5-Bromo-2-furoncarboxylic acid (114.5 mg, 0.6 mmol) was taken. The crude compound was purified by silica gel column chromatography ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{MeOH} = 20:1$, v/v), recrystallized from MeOH/Ether to give dye **LG3** (yield 69%) as a green solid. Anal. Calcd. For $\text{C}_{93}\text{H}_{109}\text{N}_5\text{O}_7\text{SZn}$ (1506.33): C, 74.15; H, 7.29; N, 4.65. Found: C, 74.12; H, 7.20; N, 4.61. MALDI-TOF: m/z $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^+$ calcd. for $\text{C}_{93}\text{H}_{109}\text{N}_5\text{O}_7\text{SZn}$, 1506.33; found, 1505.45. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz): $\delta=9.63$ (d, $J=4.4$ Hz, 2 H), 9.56 (d, $J=4.8$ Hz, 2 H), 8.90 (dd, $J=10.1$ Hz, 6.2 Hz, 4 H), 8.00 (s, 1 H), 7.81 – 7.75 (m, 4 H), 7.71 (s, 2 H), 7.57 (d, $J=7.0$ Hz, 2 H), 7.51 (d, $J=2.7$ Hz, 1 H), 7.17 (d, $J=6.6$ Hz, 2 H), 7.11 (s, 2 H), 6.95 (d, $J=7.7$ Hz, 2 H), 3.91 (m, 10 H), 1.27 (s, 6 H), 0.95 (m, 10 H), 0.91 (m, 8 H), 0.71 (m, 12 H), 0.62 – 0.53 (m, 29 H), 0.45 – 0.37 ppm (m, 10 H). FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}): 3424, 2924, 2854, 2156, 1728, 1588, 1499, 1459, 1377, 1339, 1248, 1206, 1142, 1096, 995, 792, 763, 718.

[5,15-bis(2,6-dioctoxyphenyl)-10-(3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine)-20-(4-(7-benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl) carboxyphenylethynyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) LG6. We have adopted similar procedure as **LG1**, but only the difference is instead of 4-iodobenzoic acid, 4-(7-bromobenzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)benzoic acid (**2**) (196.2 mg, 0.58 mmol) was taken. The crude compound was purified by silica gel column chromatography ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{MeOH} = 20:1$, v/v), recrystallized from MeOH/Ether to give dye **LG6** (yield 66%) as a green solid. Anal. Calcd. For $\text{C}_{101}\text{H}_{113}\text{N}_7\text{O}_6\text{S}_2\text{Zn}$ (1650.53): C, 73.50; H, 6.90; N, 5.94. Found: C, 73.42; H, 6.95; N, 5.90. MALDI-TOF: m/z $[\text{M}]^+$ calcd. for $\text{C}_{101}\text{H}_{113}\text{N}_7\text{O}_6\text{S}_2\text{Zn}$, 1650.53; found, 1650.85. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz): $\delta=10.03$ (d, $J=4.5$ Hz, 2 H), 9.64 (d, $J=4.5$ Hz, 2 H), 9.00 (d, $J=4.5$ Hz, 2 H), 8.91 (d, $J=5.5$ Hz, 2 H), 8.42 (d, $J=8.2$ Hz, 2 H), 8.19 (dd, $J=7.8$ Hz, 4.2 Hz, 3 H), 7.91 (s, 1 H), 7.90 – 7.69 (m, 4 H), 7.62 (d, $J=5.1$ Hz, 2 H), 7.62 (s, 1 H), 7.56 – 7.07 (m, 4 H), 7.07 – 6.93 (m, 2 H), 3.91 (t, $J=6.3$ Hz, 10 H), 1.28 (d, $J=7.2$ Hz, 6 H), 1.01 – 0.94 (m, 8 H), 0.89 (dd, $J=8.8$ Hz, 5.7 Hz, 11 H), 0.84 – 0.76 (m, 10 H), 0.59 – 0.55 (m, 30 H), 0.46 ppm (10 H, m). FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}): 3448, 2923, 2852, 2182, 1686, 1586, 1497, 1459, 1336, 1245, 1208, 1097, 995, 884, 762, 715, 533.

[5,15-bis(2,6-dioctoxyphenyl)-10-(3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine)-20-(2-(7-benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl) carboxythiophene-5-ethynyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) LG7. We have adopted similar procedure as LG1, but only the difference is instead of 4-iodobenzoic acid, 5-(7-bromobenzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (197.9 mg, 0.58 mmol) was taken. The crude compound was purified by silica gel column chromatography (CH₂Cl₂/MeOH = 20:1, v/v), recrystallized from MeOH/Ether to give dye LG7 (yield 59%) as a green solid. Anal.Calcd. For C₉₉H₁₁₁N₇O₆S₃Zn% (1656.56): C, 71.78; H, 6.75; N, 5.92. Found: C, 71.83; H, 6.70; N, 5.90.MALDI-TOF: m/z [MH]⁺calcd. for C₉₉H₁₁₁N₇O₆S₃Zn, 1656.56; found 1656.48. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz): δ=9.99 (d, J=4.4 Hz, 2 H), 9.62 (d, J=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.97 (d, J=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.89 (d, J=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.07 (d, J=4.4 Hz, 1 H), 8.03 (d, J=6.4 Hz, 1 H), 7.83 (d, J=3.6 Hz, 1 H), 7.66 (s, 4 H), 7.60 (d, J=4.2 Hz, 2 H), 7.30 (m, 1 H), 7.08 (s, 1 H), 6.94 (m, 4 H), 6.88 (m, 2 H), 3.88 (t, J=4.6 Hz, 8 H), 3.79 (t, J=3.6 Hz, 2 H), 1.27 (s, 10 H), 0.94 (s, 4 H), 0.86 (m, 11 H), 0.73 – 0.68 (m, 10 H), 0.57 (d, J=6.0 Hz, 30 H), 0.47 – 0.43 ppm (m, 10 H). FT-IR (neat, cm⁻¹): 3453, 2924, 2853, 2179, 1709, 1629, 1515, 1458, 1377, 1250, 1174, 1096, 761.

2.2.2. LG4 & LG5. We have adopted similar procedure as **LG1**, but only the difference is instead of 4-iodobenzoic acid, we have taken either 4-Bromobenzaldehyde or 5-Bromo-2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde to get the corresponding intermediates **LG4a** or **LG5a**, respectively..

[5,15-bis(2,6-dioctoxyphenyl)-10-(3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine)-20-(4-formylphenylethynyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) LG4a. Anal. Calcd. For C₉₅H₁₁₁N₅O₅SZn%: C, 76.05; H, 7.46; N, 4.67. Found: C, 76.13; H, 7.45; N, 4.62. MALDI-TOF: m/z [M-H]⁺calcd. for C₉₅H₁₁₁N₅O₅SZn, 1500.37; found, 1498.31.62. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz): δ=10.05 (s, 1 H), 9.62 (dd, J=7.2 Hz, 4.5 Hz, 4 H), 8.88 (d, J=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.85 (d, J=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.04 (d, J=8.0 Hz, 2 H), 7.98 (d, J=8.0 Hz, 2 H), 7.74 (dd, J=17.2 Hz, 8.5 Hz, 4 H), 7.19 (t, J=5.9 Hz, 2 H), 7.01 (d, J=8.6 Hz, 5 H), 6.96 (s, 1 H), 6.93 (d, J=8.4 Hz, 1 H), 3.94 (d, J=7.3 Hz, 2 H), 3.86 (t, J=6.4 Hz, 8 H), 1.28 (m, 4 H), 0.98 (m, 8 H), 0.91 – 0.87 (m, 5 H), 0.83 – 0.79 (m, 8 H), 0.61 (dd, J=14.9 Hz, 7.4 Hz, 10 H), 0.56 – 0.48 (m, 30 H), 0.42 ppm (m, 10 H). FT-IR (neat, cm⁻¹): 3449, 2923, 2853, 1636, 1460, 1214, 1096, 763, 553.

[5,15-bis(2,6-dioctoxyphenyl)-10-(3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine)-20-(2-formylthiophene-5-ethynyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) LG5a. Anal. Calcd. For

C₉₃H₁₀₉N₅O₅S₂Zn% (1506.40): C, 76.05; H, 7.46; N, 4.67. Found: C, 76.13; H, 7.45; N, 4.62. MALDI-TOF: m/z [M-H]⁺calcd. for C₉₃H₁₀₉N₅O₅S₂Zn, 1506.40; found, 1507.52. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz): δ=10.05 (s, 1 H), 9.63 – 9.61 (m, 4 H), 8.88 (d, *J*=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.85 (d, *J*=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.04 (s, 1 H), 7.97 (s, 1 H), 7.76 (dd, *J*=8.3 Hz, 1.8 Hz, 1 H), 7.73 – 7.71 (m, 2 H), 7.70 (s, 1 H), 7.21 – 7.18 (m, 2 H), 7.01 (d, *J*=8.6 Hz, 5 H), 6.98 – 6.94 (m, 2 H), 3.95 (d, *J*=7.1 Hz, 2 H), 3.86 (t, *J*=6.4 Hz, 10 H), 3.44 (d, *J*=7.0 Hz, 2 H), 2.92 (s, 2 H), 2.84 – 2.80 (m, 2 H), 1.97 (s, 1 H), 1.89 (dd, *J*=14.9 Hz, 7.5 Hz, 3 H), 1.51 (s, 8 H), 1.20 – 1.17 (m, 4 H), 0.98 (s, 4 H), 0.88 – 0.81 (m, 9 H), 0.64 – 0.61 (m, 8 H), 0.54 – 0.49 (m, 29 H), 0.45 – 0.40 ppm (m, 10 H). FT-IR (neat, cm⁻¹): 3451, 2924, 2853, 1633, 1458, 1218, 1097, 771.

2.2.3. General procedure for synthesis of LG4 & LG5. Either **LG4a** or **LG5a** (0.07 mmol) and cyanoacetic acid (110 mg, 0.14 mmol) and catalytic amount of piperidine was dissolved in 10 mL of CH₃CN/CHCl₃(3/1). The resultant reaction mixture was refluxed for 8 h. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was washed with 0.1 M HCl and water and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic layer dried and purified by silica gel column chromatography (CH₂Cl₂/MeOH = 20/1) as the eluent.

[5,15-bis(2,6-dioctoxyphenyl)-10-(3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine)-20-(4-acryloxyphenylethynyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) LG4. 80% yield. Anal. Calcd. For C₉₈H₁₁₂N₆O₆SZn% (1567.42): C, 75.09; H, 7.20; N, 5.36. Found: C, 75.13; H, 7.25; N, 5.30. MALDI-TOF: m/z [M]⁺calcd. for C₉₈H₁₁₂N₆O₆SZn, 1567.42; found, 1567.62. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ=9.63 (d, *J*=4.4 Hz, 1 H), 9.46 (dd, *J*=4.4 Hz, 2.2 Hz, 3 H), 9.44 (d, *J*=4.5 Hz, 4 H), 9.01 (s, 2 H), 8.91 – 8.85 (m, 4 H), 8.83 (s, 1 H), 7.78 – 7.70 (m, 4 H), 7.69 (s, 1 H), 7.16 (d, *J*=11.8 Hz, 2 H), 7.12 (m, 2 H), 7.05 (d, *J*=7.1 Hz, 2 H), 3.92 – 3.85 (m, 8 H), 3.84 (s, 2 H), 1.29 – 1.27 (m, 6 H), 0.89 (s, 10 H), 0.79 (s, 10 H), 0.62 (m, 10 H), 0.57 – 0.49 (m, 29 H), 0.47 ppm (m, 10 H). FT-IR (neat, cm⁻¹): 3450, 2924, 2854, 1741, 1588, 1552, 1459, 1375, 1253, 1097, 1014, 769.

[5,15-bis(2,6-dioctoxyphenyl)-10-(3-ethynyl-10-octyl-10H-phenothiazine)-20-(2-acryloxythiophene-5-ethynyl)porphyrinato] Zinc(II) LG5. 79% yield. Anal. Calcd. For C₉₆H₁₁₀N₆O₆S₂Zn% (1573.45): C, 73.28; H, 7.05; N, 5.34. Found: C, 73.23; H, 7.00; N, 5.30. MALDI-TOF: m/z [M-H]⁺calcd. for C₉₆H₁₁₀N₆O₆S₂Zn, 1573.45; found, 1572.71. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz): δ=9.60 (d, *J*=4.5 Hz, 2 H), 9.55 (d, *J*=7.5 Hz, 2 H), 8.92 (d, *J*=4.6 Hz, 4 H), 7.77 (s, 1 H), 7.72 (d, *J*=3.2 Hz, 2 H), 7.71 (d, *J*=3.2 Hz, 2 H), 7.66 (m, 3 H), 7.16

(m, 2 H), 7.12– 7.06 (m, 4 H), 6.95 – 6.92 (d, $J=3.5$ Hz, 2 H), 3.89 (t, $J=8.2$ Hz, 10 H), 1.28 (d, $J=4.0$ Hz, 6 H), 0.91 (d, $J=1.0$ Hz, 8 H), 0.72– 0.69 (dd, $J=7.9$ Hz, 3.3 Hz, 10 H), 0.65 – 0.60 (m, 10 H), 0.59 – 0.50 (m, 29 H), 0.48 – 0.39 ppm (m, 10 H). FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}): 3449, 2923, 2853, 1742, 1629, 1500, 1459, 1376, 1212, 1161, 1097, 768, 465.

2.3. Methods and Instrumentation.

^1H NMR spectra were obtained at 300 MHz using a Bruker 300 Avance NMR spectrometer running X-WIN NMR software. The elemental analyses were done on an Elementar, Vario MICRO CUBE analyzer. Differential pulse and cyclic voltammetric measurements were performed on a PC-controlled CH instruments model CHI 620C electrochemical analyzer. Cyclic voltammetric experiments were performed on 1 mM sample solution in tetrahydrofuran solvent at scan rate of 100 mV/s using 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as supporting electrolyte. The working electrode is glassy carbon, standard calomel electrode (SCE) is reference electrode and platinum wire is an auxiliary electrode. After a cyclic voltammogram (CV) had been recorded, ferrocene was added, and a second voltammogram was measured.

2.3.1. Absorption steady state and time resolved fluorescence measurements. The optical absorption spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu (Model UV-3600) spectrophotometer. Concentrations of solutions are ca. 1×10^{-6} M for Soret band and 1×10^{-5} M for Q band absorption. Steady state fluorescence spectra were recorded (Spex model Fluorlog-3) for solutions having optical density at the wavelength of excitation (λ_{ex}) ≈ 0.11 . Time-resolved fluorescence measurements have been carried out using HORIBA Jobin Yvon spectrofluorometer. Briefly, the samples were excited at 650 nm and the emission was monitored at 780 nm. The count rates employed were typically $10^3 - 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Deconvolution of the data was carried out by the method of iterative reconvolution of the instrument response function and the assumed decay function using DAS-6 software. The goodness of the fit of the experimental data to the assumed decay function was judged by the standard statistical tests (*i.e.*, random distribution of weighted residuals, the autocorrelation function and the values of reduced χ^2).

2.3.2. Theoretical Calculations. All the calculations have been carried out using a Gaussian 09 package in personal computer.³⁸ The obtained geometries of all the dyes **LG1** - **LG7** were stable in their conformation with global minimum energy. B3LYP hybrid functional³⁹ and 6-

31G (d,p) basis set⁴⁰ were used as the input for further calculations. We have executed ground state properties like energy-minimized structures, frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) by Density Functional Theory (DFT) in the gas phase. Time Dependent Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) carried out to obtain excited state properties like percentage of molecular contribution, oscillatory strength, singlet transition energy in the tetrahydrofuran solvent. The integral equation formalism polarizable continuum model (PCM)^{41,42} within the self-consistent reaction field (SCRF) theory was used in the TDDFT calculations to describe with M06-2x function and the solvation of the dyes in tetrahydrofuran. The software GaussSum 2.2.5 was employed to simulate the major portions of the absorption spectra and to interpret the nature of transitions.^{43,44} The contribution percentages of individual units present in the dyes to the respective molecular orbitals were calculated.

2.3.3. Device fabrication. The TiO₂ photoanode was prepared as reported previously.⁴⁵ A fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) conducting glass substrate with a resistance of $\sim 10 \text{ ohm}^{-2}$ were used. A screen printed double layer TiO₂ film of (8+5) μm in thickness (0.25 cm² cell area) with a 8- μm transparent layer of TiO₂ particles (approximately 20 nm in diameter) and a 5- μm scattering layer of TiO₂ particles (approximately 400 nm in diameter) was prepared. The films were sintered at 500 °C for 1 h. The thickness of the films was measured with a Surfcom 1400A surface profiler (Tokyo Seimitsu Co. Ltd.). A 0.2 mM solution of dye in 1:1 (v/v) acetonitrile/*tert*-butyl alcohol was used to coat the TiO₂ film. The TiO₂ films were immersed in the dye solutions and then kept at 25°C for 15 h. To assemble each cell, each dye-coated TiO₂ film and a platinum-coated conducting glass were separated by a Surlyn spacer (40 μm thick) and sealed by heating the polymer frame at 100°C. An electrolyte consisting of a mixture of 0.6 M dimethylpropyl-imidazolium iodide, 0.05 M I₂, 0.1M LiI, and 0.5M *tert*-butylpyridine in acetonitrile was used in each cell. The current–voltage characteristics were measured using a black metal mask with an area of 0.25 cm² under A M 1.5 sunlight (100 mWcm⁻², WXS-155S-10: Wacom Denso Co. Japan). The IPCE spectra were measured with a monochromatic incident light of 1×10^{16} photons cm⁻² in direct current mode (CEP-2000BX, Bunko-Keiki).

2.3.4. Transient absorption spectroscopy. A laser flash photolysis spectrometer (model LP920, Edinburg) has been used. It was associated with a Continuum Nd-YAG laser (Surelite; 10 Hz repetition rate; FWHM 5 ns). A Surelite optical parametric oscillator permits conversion of the second harmonic to a visible spectrum 400-820 nm. The respective dyes

were excited at 445 nm. The excited state decay of the dye and the recovery of its fundamental state were monitored by the change in the absorbed continuous wave light. Satisfactory signal-to-noise ratio was obtained by averaging absorption spectra for 100-200 laser shots.

2.3.5. CEM and IMVS measurements. The photovoltaic response induced by the modulated light was studied by using intensity-modulated photo voltage spectroscopy (IMVS). A potentiostat (Solartron1287) equipped with a frequency response analyzer (Solartron1255B) at an open-circuit condition, based on a monochromatic illumination (420 nm) controlled by Lab view system was used to measure IMVS. The modulated light was driven with a 10% AC perturbation current superimposed on a DC current in a frequency range from 0.1 to 106 Hz. The charge extraction method (CEM) was performed with the same monochromatic light source. The solar cell was illuminated at an open-circuit condition for 5 s to attain a steady state and then the light source was switched off when the device simultaneously switched to a short-circuit condition to extract the charges generated at that light intensity.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Synthesis

The synthesis of all novel porphyrin sensitizers is illustrated in Schemes 1 and 2. The compounds **1**, **2**, **3**, & **4** were synthesized by adopting procedure reported elsewhere.^{31,36,37} The vital intermediate **5** was synthesized by Sonogashira coupling reaction between compound **1** and **4** (Scheme 1).⁴⁶ The sensitizers **LG1**, **LG2**, **LG3**, **LG6**, and **LG7** were synthesized by deprotection of TIPS-acetylene of **5** with corresponding bromo aromatic acid by using AsPh_3 and $\text{Pd}_2(\text{dba})_3$ reagents followed by column chromatography purification to get the desired sensitizer (Scheme 2). On the other hand, **LG4**, and **LG5** were synthesized indirectly by deprotection of TIPS-acetylene of compound **5** with corresponding bromo aromatic aldehyde to get intermediate **LG4a** and **LG5a**. Finally these intermediates reacted with cyanoacetic acid in presence of piperidine (knoevenagel condensation) to get **LG4** and **LG5** sensitizers (Scheme 2). All these sensitizers were fully characterized by elemental analysis, ^1H NMR, MALDI-TOF-MS, IR, UV-Visible, fluorescence spectroscopic techniques as well as electrochemical methods. The mass spectral data of all these sensitizers are having molecular ion peak to their corresponding molecular weight (*See* Supporting Information Figure S1-S22).

Scheme 1: The synthetic route for intermediate compound (5).

Scheme 2: i.TBAF, THF, 0°C; Pd₂(dba)₃, AsPh₃, TEA, reflux, 17 h; ii.Cyanoacetic acid, piperidine, reflux, 8h.

3.2. Optical Properties

The optical absorption spectra of **LG1-LG7** sensitizers were measured in THF solvent and representative absorption spectra of **LG5** and **LG6** are exemplified in Figure 1. The corresponding wavelength of absorption maxima (λ_{max}) and logarithmic of molar extinction coefficients (ϵ) of **LG1-LG7** are given in Table 1. These porphyrins exhibited characteristic intense Soret band at (~ 460 nm), an $a_{1u}(\pi)/eg(\pi^*)$ electronic transition, which is assigned to the second excited state (S_2). The Q-bands (550-750nm) due to $a_{2u}(\pi)/eg(\pi^*)$ electronic transition, are assigned as the first excited state (S_1). Table 1 clearly showed that the switching of the phenyl and furan moieties to thiophene results in a red shift of Q band in **LG2** by 6 nm compared to the **LG1** and **LG3** dyes. It indicates that the excited state is more polar than the ground state due to insertion of thiophene unit as π -spacer.^{21,31} This result demonstrates hetero-aromatic unit (thiophene acting as the π -spacer) have a significant impact on the absorption spectra of porphyrin dyes. Change of anchoring group from carboxylic acid (**LG1-LG3**) to cyanoacrylic acid in (**LG4 & LG5**) dyes exhibits a further red shift in both Soret and Q band absorption, suggesting efficient intra-molecular charge transfer (CT) behaviour (*See* Figure S23). Elongation of π -conjugation and loss of symmetry in **LG4** and **LG5** are also two important strategies for broadening the light-harvesting area of porphyrin dyes.¹⁸ Incorporation of the benzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazole (BTD) moiety as auxiliary acceptor between the porphyrin π -spacer and anchoring carboxylic acid resulted in, an enormous change on the absorption spectra of **LG6** and **LG7** than **LG1-LG5**. Compared to **LG1-LG5**, the electronic transition in **LG6** and **LG7** with a dominant HOMO to LUMO contribution was expected to exhibit an enhanced CT character and it is most evident by the absorption between the Soret and Q bands (450–550 nm). Furthermore, the absorption of **LG6** and **LG7** displayed significant shift towards near IR region leading to the panchromatic character of the BTD-functionalized porphyrin dyes (*See* Figure S23). Figure S24 depicted the simulated absorption spectra of **LG5** and **LG6** porphyrin systems obtained from TD-DFT calculations. The emission spectra of all newly synthesized D- π -A porphyrin sensitizers were measured at room temperature in THF solvent and the representative spectra of **LG5** and **LG6** are illustrated in Figure 1. The corresponding emission maxima and their quantum yields are reported in Table 1. The emission intensities are comparable among all these porphyrin sensitizers the trend in emission red shift is similar to the trend of their Q band absorption spectra. The emission spectra of **LG4 & LG5** show a further red shifted feature,

Figure 1: Absorption (left) and emission (right) spectra of porphyrin sensitizers **LG5** and **LG6** in THF solvent. Simulated absorption bands are shown as vertical bars.

Table 1: Photophysical properties of porphyrin sensitizers

Sensitizer	Absorption,			Emission,		$\tau^{\text{d,ns}}$	E_{0-0}	E_{OX}	$E^*\text{OX}$
	λ_{max} (nm),			λ_{em} (nm) ^b ,	$(\Phi)^{\text{c}}$	(A %)	(eV) ^e	(V) ^f /	(V) ^g
	(Log ϵ ,(M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)) ^a							SCE	
LG1	457	586	662	672		1.62(100)	1.87	0.80	-1.07
	(5.43)	(3.95)	(4.78)	(0.17)					
LG2	459	585	667	678		1.54(100)	1.86	0.80	-1.06
	(5.30)	(3.85)	(4.60)	(0.11)					
LG3	457	579	639	661	672	1.18(57)	1.88	0.81	-1.07
	(5.49)	(4.16)	(4.52)	(4.56)	(0.18)	2.07(43)			
LG4	461	591	676	685		1.06(73)	1.80	0.79	-1.01
	(5.22)	(3.94)	(4.72)	(0.17)		2.11(27)			
LG5	467	588	687	688		1.64(66)	1.80	0.82	-0.98
	(5.20)	(3.93)	(4.85)	(0.27)		1.75(34)			
LG6	462	623	681	700		1.51(100)	1.80	0.78	-1.02
	(5.26)	(4.18)	(4.95)	(0.26)					
LG7	453	637	690	709		0.93(64)	1.78	0.77	-1.01
	(4.87)	(4.31)	(4.80)	(0.10)		2.00(36)			

^aSolvent: ethanol, Error limits: λ_{max} , ± 1 nm, $\epsilon \pm 10\%$. ^bError limits: λ_{em} , ± 1 nm. ^c ϕ , $\pm 0.01\%$. ^dError limits $\tau \sim 10\%$. ^e E_{0-0} was determined from the intersection of absorption and emission spectra, as shown in Fig. 1, Figure S23, and S25; ^fSolvent: THF, error limits: $E_{\text{ox}} \pm 0.03$ V, 0.1 M TBAP. ^g E^*_{ox} was determined as $E_{\text{ox}} - E_{0-0}$.

this phenomenon indicates that electronic coupling between cyanoacrylic acid and porphyrin ring was more effective. Furthermore, the similar type of effect observed in **LG6** and **LG7** dyes by incorporating BTD moiety between porphyrin π -spacer and anchoring carboxylic acid. From Table 1, it is clear that the quantum yields of all porphyrin sensitizers is enhanced in comparison with reference compound 5,10,15,20-tetraphenyl zinc porphyrin (ZnTPP) (Figure S25).⁴⁷ The singlet state energies (E_{0-0}) of all porphyrin sensitizers, estimated from excitation and emission spectra are presented in Table 1. They are found in the range of $\sim 1.83 \pm 0.05$ eV, which is less, than the value of the reference compound, ZnTPP. No emission spectra were observed for **LG1-LG7** adsorbed onto 6 μm thick TiO_2 layer as a consequence of electron injection from excited singlet state of porphyrin into the conduction band of TiO_2 . The singlet excited life-time of all seven porphyrin sensitizers were measured in THF solvent and found in the range of ~ 1.50 ns, typical life-time of its reference ZnTPP (See Figure S26).⁴⁸ In all seven sensitizers the excited state life-time quenched when adsorbed onto 6 μm thick TiO_2 layer.

3.3. Electrochemical and Spectroelectrochemical Studies

With a view to evaluate the HOMO-LUMO levels of newly designed porphyrin sensitizers, we have performed cyclic voltammetry studies using 0.1 M TBAP in THF solvent as supporting electrolyte with an internal reference of Fc/Fc^+ . Each sensitizer exhibited two reversible oxidation and one quasi-reversible reduction processes. The first oxidation process of all seven sensitizers is illustrated in Figure 2 and corresponding redox data is presented in Table 1. It showed that first oxidation (E_{OX}) at ~ 0.78 V vs. SCE. The excited state oxidation potential (E^*_{OX}) of each porphyrin sensitizer was calculated using an expression, $E^*_{\text{OX}} = E_{\text{OX}} - E_{0-0}$, and found above the conduction band of TiO_2 .⁴⁹ Figure 3 represents an energy level diagram of **LG1-LG7** dyes, indicating that efficient dye regeneration and electron injection processes for **LG1- LG7** dye-sensitized TiO_2 systems are energetically favourable. Among all sensitizers, **LG5** and **LG6** dyes are more favourable for electron injection and dye regeneration and can expect high efficiency (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Cyclic voltammograms of **LG1-LG7** porphyrins in THF/0.1 M TBAP.

Figure 3: An energy-level diagram of **LG1-LG7** porphyrins, electrolyte and TiO₂; $E_{(\text{HOMO})} = E_{\text{oxd}}$ and $E_{(\text{LUMO})} = E_{(\text{HOMO})} - E_{0-0}$.

In DSSC, the sensitizer gets excited by absorbing a photon and injects electron from its excited state into TiO₂ conduction band on an ultra-rapid time scale. Spectro-electrochemical studies were performed gain insight into the electronic properties of the oxidized species of the porphyrin sensitizers.⁵⁰ Figure 4 shows the spectral changes of **LG5** under an applied potential. During the controlled potential oxidation of **LG5** at +0.90 V, the absorption Q band at 675 nm decreases its intensity with a significant hypsochromic shift of 20 nm, with formation of new band at 562 nm. The Soret band at 462 nm also decreases its intensity and the formation of a new band at 433 with increasing its intensity. In contrast, the

spectral region corresponds to the donor phenothiazine moiety show an increase in intensity. During this process clear isosbestic points were observed at 438 nm, 541 nm, and 603 nm, which clearly indicate that the oxidation gives a single product. These characteristic changes indicate the formation of the porphyrin cation radical.⁵¹ Although the oxidation was observed to be reversible during cyclic voltammetry, the porphyrin cation radical generated at +0.90 V cannot be fully recovered to its neutral form when the applied potential changed to +0.2 V. This may be due to the degradation of **LG5** during longer time-scale of the spectroelectrochemical study. The newly generated porphyrin radical after spectroelectrochemical study shows similar characteristic of a porphyrin, this is likely due to some chemical changes to the substituent groups. From the results it is anticipated that **LG5** sensitizer is exhibiting greater oxidative stability during spectroelectrochemical studies than the well-known Ru-sensitizer N719 under similar conditions which essential during the operation of the solar cell.^{51,52} Similar type of spectral changes are also observed in other porphyrin sensitizer (Figure S28).

Figure 4. Oxidative OTTLE studies of **LG5** in 0.3M TBAP/THF with an applied potential of +0.90V (vs. SCE/KCl).

3.4. Theoretical Studies

Figure 5. Isodensity (0.02) plots of FMOs and the energy values in eV by using B3LYP method 6-31G(d,p).

To understand the structural, electronic, and optical properties of the dyes **LG1-LG7**, DFT and TDDFT calculations with functional basis set of B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level were performed. Figure S27 shows the ground state optimized structures of **LG1-LG7**, comprises donor and acceptor moieties separating the porphyrin ring with ethynyl π -spacer, which keeps the dye in one plane. It is observed that the PTZ moiety, in its neutral state, is bent around the N-S axis with an angle of $\sim 147^\circ$, which is in agreement with the value reported in the literature.⁵³ Anchoring group of all the dyes were in plane with porphyrin plane, except **LG4** (deviation 24°) and **LG6** (deviation 33°) and this may effect on efficiency. Figure 5 shows frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) of the **LG1-LG7** dyes. Table S1 shows HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-LUMO gap energies and ground state dipole moment in Debye units. In all sensitizers, the electron density distribution of HOMO and LUMO is occupied partially on donor, porphyrin and acceptor moieties and in HOMO-1, LUMO+1 the electron density mainly on porphyrin moiety only. However, in HOMO-2 it is located mostly on donor moiety and slightly on porphyrin ring and in LUMO+2 it is located mostly on acceptor group except in **LG6** & **LG7** and slightly on porphyrin ring, which might effect on efficiency of the device too. From this one can explain the electron transfer from donor phenothiazine to acceptor group *via* porphyrin ring and these HOMO-LUMO gaps of a dye systems followed the order: **LG1** > **LG3** > **LG2** > **LG4** \approx **LG5** \approx **LG6** > **LG7**. Further, TD-DFT studies on these molecules were carried at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level for further understanding of the excited-state transitions with the framework of the polarizable continuum model (PCM) in tetrahydrofuran as solvent with M06-2X function. These results are in reasonable agreement with the experimental values. The calculated vertical excitation energies for singlet together with calculated oscillator strengths are listed in Table S2.

3.5. Device Studies

Figure 6: (a) Photocurrent action spectra and (b) Current–voltage characteristics of **LG1-LG7** sensitizers. TBP concentration 0.1M.

The photovoltaic performance *i.e.*, the incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) and photocurrent- voltage (J - V) characteristics, were assessed by test devices using standard mesoporous 8 μm thick TiO_2 films and an acetonitrile- based electrolyte composed of 0.6 M 1,2-dimethyl-3-propylimidazolium iodide (DMPII), 0.05 M I_2 , 0.1 M LiI and 0.1 M 4-tert-butylpyridine (TBP). The detailed fabrication method was described in our earlier studies.^{9,46} The photocurrent action spectra of **LG1-LG7** sensitizers are shown in Figure 6a. The IPCE spectra of **LG2**, **LG3**, **LG4** and **LG7** porphyrin dyes showed two maxima at ~ 480 and ~ 700 nm attributed to the Soret band and Q- band absorption. Whereas Soret and Q-bands were merged in **LG1**, **LG5** and **LG6** dyes and appeared as a single band. We observed IPCE value of greater than 80% for **LG1**, **LG5** and **LG6** dyes at 600 nm. The onset of IPCE extended up to 850 nm in all sensitizers except **LG5** where it extended up to 900 nm.

Figure 6b shows the J - V curves of **LG1-LG7** dyes. Table-2 summarizes the cell performance parameters such as open-circuit potential (V_{oc}), short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), fill factor (**FF**) and energy conversion efficiency (η) of the porphyrin sensitizers. Among the fabricated DSSCs, the efficiency (η) in carboxylic acid anchoring group with phenyl, thiophene, furan as π -spacer porphyrin dyes such as **LG1** (8.89%) is 11.4% and 30.5% higher than that of **LG2** (7.87%) and **LG3** (6.17%) because of the enhancement of J_{sc} values from those of the **LG2** and **LG3** dyes.

Figure 7: (a) Photocurrent action spectra and (b) J - V characteristics of **LG5** sensitizer using different concentrations of TBP.

These results revealed that the more electron-withdrawing nature of thiophene and phenyl groups than furan group results in better efficiency. **LG5** exhibited the energy conversion efficiency (η) of 10.20%, which is 28.5% higher than that of the **LG4** (7.30%) due to higher J_{sc} -value. Moreover, as a general feature, the presence of a cyanoacrylic acid group on the “pull” ethynylthiophene substituent of the porphyrin **LG5** was found to produce superior DSSC performances than ethynylphenyl “pull” ethynylthiophene substituent bearing the anchoring group. The introduction of the 2,1,3-benzothiadiazole (BDT) group between the porphyrin macrocycle and π -spacer carboxylic acid with a phenyl group for **LG6** and a thiophene group for **LG7** tethered to carboxylic acid as secondary acceptor resulted in the energy conversion efficiency of 9.64% for **LG6** and 6.21% for **LG7**. The η value for the **LG6** is 35.5% higher than that of **LG7**, which is due to higher J_{sc} value.

3.6. Kinetic Studies

It is a well-known fact that the addition of TBP in the redox-couple electrolyte shifts the semiconductor's conduction band edge and improves the photovoltaic performance of DSSC.⁵⁴ In order to standardize the concentration of TBP additive in redox electrolyte, we added different concentration of TBP and studied its effect on IPCE and cell performance parameters. Figure 7a illustrates representative IPCE spectra of **LG5** sensitizer with TBP concentration of 0.1, 0.3 and 0.5 M. The IPCE data at 600 nm of all seven sensitizers are given in Table 2, which indicated a detrimental effect of the TBP on the IPCE (*See* Figure S28). Figure 7b shows a representative J-V curve of **LG5** sensitizer with TBP concentration of 0.1, 0.3 and 0.5M. The photovoltaic cell performance data of **LG1-LG7** dyes are presented in Table 2 for direct comparison. One can note that an increase in concentration of TBP from

Figure 8: V_{oc} as a function of electron density for DSSCs sensitized with **LG1-LG7**. Electron density was measured by means of a charge extraction method.

Figure 9: Electron lifetime (τ) as a function of V_{oc} for DSSCs sensitized with **LG1-LG7**. Electron lifetime was measured by means of intensity-modulated photovoltage spectroscopy.

0.1M to 0.5M marginally increased the V_{oc} -value, but decreased the J_{sc} -value, and thus the cell efficiency (See Figure S29).

To further understand the molecular structure dependent V_{OC} for **LG1-LG7**, we first measured the relative conduction band position of TiO_2 by means of a charge extraction method. Figure 8 shows V_{OC} as a function of electron density for all dyes. A linear increase in V_{OC} as a function of electron density was observed for all DSSCs. Notably, the plots for all dyes overlapped with each other, indicating that all of the dyes have almost the same effect on the conduction band of TiO_2 regardless of the various π -spacers between porphyrin macrocycle and anchoring carboxylic acid. Therefore, the molecular structure dependent V_{OC} for all DSSCs should be attributed to the extent of charge recombination that is related to the electron lifetime (τ) in TiO_2 . Intensity-modulated photovoltage spectroscopy was used to measure τ . Figure 9 shows the electron lifetime (τ) as a function of V_{OC} . At a certain electron density, τ follows the following order: **LG1** > **LG2** \approx **LG3** \approx **LG4** > **LG6** > **LG5** > **LG7**. It can be clearly seen that **LG1**, **LG2** and **LG3** with small π -spacers showed longer electron lifetime than **LG6** and **LG7** with larger π -spacers. This can be attributed to the formation of a compact dye layer on the TiO_2 surface, which reduces the concentration of I_3^- ions in the vicinity of the TiO_2 surface, which explains the electrons longer lifetime and suppression of the charge recombination reactions at the electrolyte (I_3^- ions)/ TiO_2 interface.

We have adopted nanosecond laser flash photolysis spectroscopy to investigate and compare the kinetics competition between waste recombination in one side and dye regeneration by electrolyte among **LG1-LG7** dyes, in the light of their electrical performances and electronic and energy level characteristics measured above. The kinetics of dye regeneration by electrolyte are considered to be one of crucial steps for the DSSC performance.^{55,56}

Figure 10: Transient absorbance decay profiles obtained upon nanosecond pulsed laser excitations (bandwidth 6 ns) on mesoporous TiO_2 films sensitized with **LG1-LG7** dyes at a laser excitation of 638 nm and monitored at 710-780 nm in the presence and in the absence of the LiI/I_2 electrolyte (Dyesol high performance electrolyte, ELHP) (No TBP added)

Figure 11: Relationship between J_{SC} and dye regeneration time by LiI/I_2 electrolyte of the **LG1-LG7** dyes based DSSCs.

Table 2: Photovoltaic performance parameters of porphyrin sensitizers

Sensitizer	TBP (mM)	IPCE (%) ^{a,b}	J_{SC} mA/cm ² ^a	V_{OC} (V)	FF ^a	η (%)
LG1	0.10	84	17.43	0.71	0.71	8.89
	0.30	79	16.20	0.72	0.72	8.51
	0.50	74	15.13	0.73	0.73	8.00
LG2	0.10	73	15.45	0.71	0.72	7.87
	0.30	63	13.61	0.72	0.72	7.08
	0.50	46	10.19	0.72	0.72	5.33
LG3	0.10	57	12.10	0.71	0.72	6.17

	0.30	46	9.49	0.71	0.73	4.92
	0.50	24	5.43	0.73	0.73	2.84
LG4	0.10	64	15.02	0.71	0.68	7.30
	0.30	51	12.37	0.72	0.71	6.32
	0.50	30	7.91	0.72	0.72	4.13
LG5	0.10	82	21.01	0.68	0.71	10.20
	0.30	72	18.49	0.71	0.72	9.48
	0.50	52	13.17	0.72	0.72	6.89
LG6	0.10	83	19.55	0.69	0.71	9.64
	0.30	77	18.46	0.72	0.72	9.58
	0.50	65	15.26	0.72	0.72	7.98
LG7	0.10	49	13.38	0.66	0.69	6.21
	0.30	23	6.71	0.68	0.71	3.23
	0.50	16	5.24	0.69	0.72	2.62

^aError limits: $J_{SC} \pm 0.20$ mA/cm², $V_{OC} = \pm 0.30$ mV, FF = ± 0.03 . ^bWavelength, 600nm.

The transient optical signals (or transient absorption signals ΔOD) in Figure 10, represent the concentration of oxidized dye sensitizer following photoinduced electron injection from the dye to the conduction band of TiO₂. In the absence of the LiI/I₂ electrolyte, the transient decays of the maximum absorption signals (ΔOD) of the dye (also called the bleaching of the ground states of the dye) reflect mostly the dynamics of, namely, excited state relaxation and charge recombination of photo injected electrons in TiO₂ with the oxidized dye. To be noted here, we have used higher laser energy enough to record suitable transient absorbance signals. This should not cause any significant change in the decay rate as has been also observed by Graetzel group.⁵⁷

Transient absorption spectra of **LG1-LG7** dyes on TiO₂ (no electrolyte added) were fitted using an exponential decay function, $y = A_1 \exp(-t/\tau_1) + A_2 \exp(-t/\tau_2) + y_0$, where A corresponds to amplitude, τ_1 denotes dye excited state relaxation time (ns time scale); τ_2 decay time for dye regeneration by TiO₂ injected electrons (μ s-ms time scale). In presence of electrolyte, the spectra were fitted using the function, $y = A_1 \exp(-t/\tau_1) + A_2 \exp(-t/\tau_2) + A_3 \exp(-t/\tau_3) + y_0$. Here, we mostly employ τ_2 (few μ s) for dye regeneration by I⁻ which has a large control on DSSC performance by reducing at maximum the electron recombination with oxidative dyes. In presence of electrolyte, the fitting of the decays led to dye regeneration times 2.65, 2.67, 3.87, 3.1, 1.9, 2.67 and 3.7 μ s which are faster than the competition waste recombination decay times in presence of air (no electrolyte added) 7.2,

6.4, 7.1, 5.6, 4.7, 8.4 and 4.4, respectively for **LG1-LG7** dyes, thus, it allows a better collection of photoinjected electrons into external circuit. Figure 11 shows, within bar errors, a close linearship between collected shortcircuit current density and the time constants of the dye regeneration by electrolyte. This close linearship corroborates well with the fact that a faster dye regeneration by electrolyte decay has allowed a higher current density collected.

Figure 12. TG/DTG curves of **LG5** with heating rate $10^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ under nitrogen gas.

We also studied the thermal stability of the **LG1-LG7** porphyrin sensitizers by using thermogravimetric analysis. The thermal stability is very essential for the durability of DSSC devices. It is well known in the literature that tetraphenyl porphyrin and its metallo derivatives are thermally stable up to 400°C .⁵⁸ Figure 12 shows the thermal behaviour of **LG5** and it is clear that the sensitizers stable up to 200°C . The initial weight loss ($\sim 2\%$) observed between 200 and 250°C is attributed to the removal of the carboxyl group. A similar trend in thermal stability was also obtained in other sensitizers of this series (See Figure S30). It is clear from the thermal data that these dyes are highly durable for longstanding outdoor applications.

3.2. Durability Studies

Figure 13: Evolutions of photovoltaic performance parameters for LG5 based DSCs during light soaking under AM 1.5 illumination (light intensity: 100 mW cm^{-2}) over a period of 1000 h. A 420 nm cut-off filter was applied during illumination. Ionic-liquid electrolyte: 0.15 M I_2 , 0.1 M GuSCN, 0.5 M MBI, and 1 M PMII in MPN at 25 °C.

A prolonged exposure of solar cells to light is expected, thus in order for DSSCs to be practically viable, long-term stability to irradiation is necessary have feature. The long-term stability of a DSSC greatly depends on the sensitizer. To test the photostability of the porphyrin sensitizer, **LG5** dye, which showed the highest efficiency device, was subjected to a light soaking test using a 420 nm cut-off filter for 1000 h as shown in Figure 13 by adopting a low volatility electrolyte composed of 0.15 M I_2 , 0.1 M GuSCN (guanidinium thiocyanate), 0.5 M MBI (1-methylbenzimidazole), and 1 M MPII (1-methyl-3-propylimidazolium iodide) in MPN (3- methoxypropionitrile). At time zero, the **LG5** based solar device with an ionic liquid electrolyte resulted in J_{SC} of 17.3 mA cm^2 , V_{OC} of 0.67 V, FF of 0.70, and η of 8.11%. A slight increase in J_{SC} and η of the devices was observed after one week, which can be attributed to the self-assembly of long alkyl chains or more efficient dye regeneration due to the penetration of the electrolyte into the hidden cavities at the **LG5** dye/ TiO_2 interface.⁵⁹ After that, V_{oc} and FF values were continually steady, but a gentle decrease was observed for J_{SC} and η values with the same trend. Under 1000 h light soaking, **LG5** dye showed good long-term stability and maintained up to more than 80% of the initial power conversion efficiency.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have designed seven new porphyrin sensitizers, **LG1–LG7**, based on D- π -A approach in which 3-ethynyl phenothiazine acts as donor, porphyrin as π -spacer and either carboxylic acid or cyanoacrylic acid as an acceptor as well as anchoring group. The introduction of secondary π -spacer alters the electronic properties of the porphyrin sensitizers. Both Soret and Q band absorption red shifted with onset extending up to 850 nm in **LG5**. The emission maxima also red shifted with significant enhancement in quantum yields of all seven new porphyrin sensitizers. DFT and TD-DFT studies showed that HOMO spread over donor and porphyrin π -spacer, LUMO spread over π -spacer and anchoring carboxylic acid groups are suitable for dye-sensitized solar cell applications. Finally, all these porphyrin sensitizers were tested DSSC using liquid I⁻/I₃⁻ redox electrolyte and found an impressive efficiency of 10.20% in case of **LG5**. Thermal studies indicate all these porphyrins are stable up to 200 °C and suitable for long-term stability. Finally, the durability studies of devices with **LG5** sensitizer using low volatile electrolyte and retain 80% initial power conversion efficiency after 1000 h of irradiation.

Acknowledgements

We thank CSIR-NISE, the Department of Science & Technology (DST), and the Government of India under the major project DST-UK ('APEX-II') for the financial support to carry out this work. NVK and JVSK thanks to CSIR and UGC for research fellowship. A. Islam and I. Bedja extend their appreciation to the International Scientific Partnership Program ISPP at King Saud University for funding this research work through ISPP #0019. A. Islam acknowledges the support of the JSPS KAKENHI grant No. 26288113.

Supporting Information

Characterization data of the compounds such as ¹H NMR (Figures **S1, S3, S5, S7, S9, S11, S13, S15, S19 & S21**), LC-MS and MALDI-MS spectra (Figures **S2, S4, S6, S8, S10, S12, S14, S16, S20 & S22**), absorption spectra in THF solvent (Figure **S23**), theoretical absorption spectra (Figure **S24**), fluorescence behaviour (Figure **S25**), Singlet excited-state lifetimes (Figure **S26**), Optimized structure of dyes (Figure **S27**), Oxidative OTTLE studies (Figure **S28**), Photocurrent action spectra porphyrin sensitizers using different concentrations of 4-tert butylpyridine (Figure **S29**), Current–voltage characteristics of porphyrin sensitizers

using different concentrations of 4-tert butylpyridine (Figure S30) and TG/DTG (Figure S31), are available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Donor- π -acceptor based stable porphyrin sensitizers for dye-sensitized solar cells: Effect of π -conjugated spacers

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